

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary of The Long-Run Effects of Psychotherapy on Depression, Beliefs, and Economic Outcomes

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Rosie Bettel¹

¹Founders Pledge

Published on: Jun 11, 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.81d3d2c5>

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: “The Long-Run Effects of Psychotherapy on Depression, Beliefs, and Economic Outcomes”. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous Evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous Evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Anon. Evaluator 1	77	4.0
Anon. Evaluator 2	92	4.7

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).²

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.³

Evaluation summaries**Anonymous evaluator 1**

This paper’s most important contribution is the evidence for sustained positive impacts on mental health after 5 years (one of the longest follow-ups in the field), after short, lower-cost (community based) therapy. As critical comments, I don’t believe the ‘depressive realism’ task was well selected, I see opportunities to better

contextualize the effects for the reader as well as opportunities to improve figures and make stronger policy recommendations.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This is a high quality paper that extensively studies the effects of therapy. I make a few small suggestions for analyses to explore the economic effects and the perceived efficacy of therapy.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴	77	(70, 84)		92	(81, 100)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁵	83	(76, 90)	6	90	(80, 100)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	75	(68, 82)	8	90	(83, 97)
Logic & communication ⁹	77	(74, 80)		79	(69, 89)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁰	35	(20, 50)	11	88	(82, 95)
Real-world relevance ¹²	83	(76, 90)	13	86	(79, 93)

Relevance to global priorities ¹⁴	85	(80, 90)		92	(82, 100)
--	----	----------	--	----	-----------

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous		Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 4.5)	4.7	(4.4, 5.0)
What ‘quality journal’ do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 4.5)	4.6	(4.1, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Unjournal process notes

The paper was brought to our attention by a suggestion from the [Happier Lives Institute](#).

One of the evaluators was a member of our Field Specialist team, but they were not part of the decision to prioritize this paper.

References

[1] Bhat, Bhargav, Jonathan de Quidt, Johannes Haushofer, Vikram Patel, Gautam Rao, Frank Schilbach, and Pierre-Luc Vautrey. *The Long-Run Effects of Psychotherapy on Depression, Beliefs, and Economic Outcomes*.

No. 17309. CEPR Discussion Papers, 2022.

Footnotes

1. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. [↵](#)
2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
3. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↵](#)
- 4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

6. The findings are relevant to global health funding prioritization particularly within mental health as a cause area. They are especially important as a contribution given the lower cost, due to training members of the community, the relatively brief duration of therapy, and the sustained long-run positive effects. At the same time, I believe the authors could draw out more explicit policy recommendations. I've tried to outline this more in my report. [↵](#)

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

8. Overall, this is a very sound paper, including two tightly controlled RCTs that seem well balanced and not impacted by attrition. Consideration of a wider dashboard of mental health measures would have strengthened the work. I'm unsure the bead bracelet task is suited to testing the question of depressive realism. Further replication in a more diverse sample would improve my confidence in the results. [↵](#)

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

10.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

11. Sufficient data is presented for meta-analysis. Some figures and their labels can be improved, see report for further info. No code or data are shared, nor is there a statement on data availability, hence low score. I've worked on many different reproducibility studies and based on this experience find that the direct and exact computational reproduction of any work where code isn't available is difficult, as researchers rarely specify 'finer' points like estimator choice, pre-processing can be opaque to a reader using only the paper, or sometimes authors will refer to citations explaining a certain method but do not report in the paper all their specification, for instance here the double ML approach. [↵](#)

12.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

13. See above on Advancing knowledge and practice. [↵](#)

14. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

References

1. Bhat, Bhargav, Jonathan de Quidt, Johannes Haushofer, Vikram Patel, Gautam Rao, Frank Schilbach, and Pierre-Luc Vautrey. *The Long-Run Effects of Psychotherapy on Depression, Beliefs, and Economic Outcomes*. No. 17309. CEPR Discussion Papers, 2022. [↵](#)